

Scientific and Creative Place of Women Potters in Uzbek Pottery and Public Attention to their Activities

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Abstract: This article details the activities of Uzbek Hamro bibi Rahimova, Kubaro Boboyeva, Nazira Kuziyeva, Dilorom Mukhtarova and young scientific creator Diyora Soliyeva. There is no clear and widespread information about famous female potters in the world, as pottery is largely a traditional and local art form, and in many cases the popularity of individual craftsmen and their work is local. However, some female potters have been able to promote their work internationally and gain recognition on the art scene.

Keywords: Potter, woman, object, ceramic toy, dragon, decorative, artistic pottery, traditional pottery, clay, glaze, research, decoration.

The history of pottery is very wide and varied. In each part of the world, it is developed differently, and its production technology is also unique. Clay has been known since ancient times as a material that man uses to satisfy his needs and wants, and pottery is one of the oldest crafts in the world. It is believed that man created the first pottery during the Neolithic period.

Since ancient times, clay has been used to make containers for storing food, grain, and water. In the oldest graves, archaeologists find molded vessels (jugs, amphorae, plates) designed for collecting and storing food, water, household items, transportation and cooking. We see images of these objects in cave paintings and the oldest frescoes, ceramic remains are frequent finds during excavations almost everywhere that ancient man lived.

Today, the oldest ceramic product is called Venus, and it is recognized by experts that the age of the product belongs to the period between 25,000 and 29,000 BC, and that its author was a female potter. Archaeologists, relying on sources, state that in primitive times women were engaged in pottery making, and later, after the discovery of the pottery wheel, men began to produce products. During this period, women potters were engaged in decorating ceramics.

Pottery is unique in different regions of Uzbekistan, and each region has its own unique methods and patterns. Women working in this field of pottery often contribute to the development of the family craft and make a living from it. There is no clear and widespread information about famous female potters in the world, as pottery is largely a traditional and local art form, and in many cases the popularity of individual craftsmen and their work is local. However, some female potters have been able to promote their work internationally and gain recognition on the art scene.

As the art of pottery often depends on individual and local talent, the level of knowledge and recognition of famous female potters can vary. Therefore, it can be helpful to check regional fairs and art centers to learn more about local artisans and their work. A number of female potters lived and worked in Uzbekistan. They were mainly engaged in decorating pottery and making small toys and toys. One such female potter is Rahimova Hamrobibi Bazar girl. He was born in 1896 in Vobkent district of Bukhara region, and he was born there. A potter who makes ceramic toys, an old traditional one small forms are considered to be a representative of sculpture.

Hamro bibi Rahimova

Hamrobibi Rahimova learned this craft (making clay toy ushpulaks, heating them in the oven, painting them) from Shamsibibi. In 1970-1975, Hamrobibi Rahimova worked in the Art Fund of the Union of Artists of Uzbekistan, in 1978-1979 in the association "Usto". Hamrobibi Rahimova is an ancient people created in the style of his art, the toys he created, enriched with simple and sincere humorous content, consisted of the shapes of horses, elephants, donkeys, rams, chickens, mares, deers, lambs, mythical birds and animals. The upper part of the toys is painted with yellow, red, green, blue paints with egg white and decorated with stripes. Samples of H. Rahimova's work are kept in the museum fund of our republic and foreign countries, including in the "Louvre" museum in Paris, in the "Faenza" world ceramics museum in Italy, and in the "Hermitage" museums of St. Petersburg. Kubaro Boboyeva, a potter who is engaged in the making of toys and bowls, one of the oldest pottery traditions, was one of the few female potters who preserved values.

From the creative work of Hamro bibi Rahimova

Kubaro Boboyeva

Kubaro Bobayeva lived and worked in the village of Uba, Bukhara region, from 1937 to 2023. Center for Ancient Ceramics. He has been modeling these toys all his life. He is a student of Hamro Rahimova, a famous craftsman from the village of Uba. He is the owner of the Order of Fame. Handicrafts that did not require much physical effort were usually done by women. Over time, traditional crafts elsewhere disappeared, and by the mid-twentieth century, only one village remained, where artisans worked their imaginations. continued to produce animals and brave riders. Unfortunately, due to the low temperature firing, these toys are very fragile. Therefore, except for museums, very few of them have been preserved.

From the creative work of Kubaro Boboyeva

Uzbek artist potter Nazira Kuziyeva was born in 1955 in Bukhara region. He studied at the ceramics department of the Republican Institute of Art Education. in the field of artistic creativity at the Pottery Department of the Tashkent State Theater and Art Institute strengthened knowledge. Artist and potter Nazira Kuziyeva became a member of the Union of Artists of Uzbekistan in 1988. Since 2003, he has been the chairman of the decorative and applied art section of the Creative Union of Artists of Uzbekistan. Unique creative works of the potter have been recognized by many art lovers. The artist-potter reflects his thoughts about life, his dreams and desires in his ceramics. Nazira Kuziyeva takes what she sees from her heart, transforms it into poetic images and presents it. That's why old themes such as pomegranate and the tree of life acquire a new look and a new meaning in Kulol's ceramic works. His "Self-Portrait", "Island Girl", "Shell", "Green Baghmal", "Walk", "Peaceful Night" and other decorative items can be an example of our above opinion.

In 2012, N. Kuziyeva was awarded the "Fame" medal of the Republic of Uzbekistan. On September 24, 2018, the opening of the personal exhibition of famous potter Nazira Kuziyeva "yelpig'ich@nippon.uz" was held at the Ikuo Hirayama International Culture Caravan Palace of the Academy of Arts of Uzbekistan. About 70 pottery samples and installations of the potter were displayed at the exhibition. The ancient art of pottery has reached us over the centuries. Ceramic works of Nazira Kuziyeva are preserved in private collections in Japan, Hungary, France, Switzerland, England, Korea, Indonesia, USA, Egypt, Germany, Latvia, Croatia, Russia.

Nazira Kuziyeva

Dilorom Mukhtarova

The master potter Dilorom Mukhtarova, the heir of the Great School of Pottery, is a representative of the finest quality among the potters of Uzbekistan. Today, they work no less than the potters who are actively working on the development of pottery. Dilorom Mukhtarovani souvenir shop is located in one of the most sacred places of Samarkand. The image of this mysterious creature associated with the dragon of the Eastern calendar has been widespread in Samarkand pottery since ancient times.

From the creative work of [Nazira Kuziyeva](#)

Dilorom Mukhtarova, a craftsman from Samarkand, is a well-known master of the famous Samarkand clay toy, whose production traditions go back to ancient times. Among its colorful products are images of various professions and animals embodied in the natural material of dragons. In ancient times, when Samarkand was attacked by enemies, the dragon flew here and helped local residents to defeat them, - says Dilorom Mukhtarova. - Therefore, the images of these mythical creatures have been widespread in the works of local ceramic masters for many centuries. Perhaps the emergence of such a tradition was influenced by the great silk road. Over the centuries, ceramics have not lost their importance. Clay toys become works of art due to the artistic expression that the master gives them. Images of dragons created from natural material are a symbol of nobility, power and patronage.

From the creative work of [Dilorom Mukhtarova](#)

Dilorom Mukhtarova is not only a creator of fantasy dragons, clowns and animals, but she is a sculptor who feels the material and knows how to convey her ideas. The renowned craftswoman is one of the few female potters who are passing on the expertise to a new generation of local ceramicists who have preserved and developed the tradition of creating unique clay toys. Today, among all fields, a number of works are being carried out in the field of fine and applied arts. This has risen to the level of state policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and a number of decisions and decrees on the development of the sector have been adopted. A number of encouraging and developmental benefits were created for artists, sculptors, miniature artists, and potters working in the field of fine and applied arts. A small proof of our above points is the fact that, starting from 2019, bachelor's education courses based on the National Institute of Painting and Design named after Kamoliddin Behzod, which is the only one in our Republic, have been established under a number of higher educational institutions of our Republic. Admission of entrants to the courses of Applied Art

(art pottery) and Rangtasvir (painting) has begun in higher education institutions. Specialists of the field have gathered in all regions to provide scientific and creative education in these areas of education. Today, one of such experts, Diyora Soliyeva, teaches the secrets of the profession to the students of Applied Art (Art Pottery) at Andijan State University. has been teaching. Today, he is a mature specialist in his field, conducting scientific research in order to develop the artistic direction of pottery in our Republic.

The branches of pottery are also expanding more and more. Naturally, there are also needs for development in terms of production. Therefore, today, the young researcher potter D. Soliyeva chose the topic "Methodology of developing the skill of students to decorate art objects based on a creative approach". In order to develop artistic ceramics, he has been studying new types of decoration and putting them into practice.

As a result of the research, it is possible to meet today's requirements and to produce alternative and ecologically clean, cheap products to imported ceramics. It can be seen from this that women are making their proper contribution in all branches of pottery production. The expected results of this are that women potters along with men have taken up their sleeves in order to deliver the variety of household and decorative pottery that satisfies all levels and needs, especially to the young generation, in the production of both traditional pottery and artistic pottery.

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